

Relation of Organization and Critical Thinking Learning Strategy with Students' Academic Performance at the University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

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Abstract: The current study intends to investigate the relationship between students' academic performance in the Department of Education at the University of Loralai, Balochistan, and the organization and critical thinking learning strategy. This quantitative study used a sample of 300 randomly selected students from the University of Lorelai's Department of Education in Balochistan. Using a legitimate and standardized MSLQ questionnaire as a data collection method, the study employed a correlation research design. Two sections of the questionnaire were distributed: one for the study and the other for the demographics. The study portion examined the relationship between students' academic performance and the organization and critical thinking learning strategies. The demographic section contained information about the students at the aforementioned university. Gender, marital status, location, age in years, number of students in class, study program, academic year, university name, department name, and GPA were among the demographic data that were measured. The current researchers employed correlational analysis to look at the relationship between students' academic performance and organization and critical thinking learning style. The current study's findings demonstrated that both organization and critical thinking learning methodologies have the least favorable impact on University of Loralai students' academic performance. This study concludes that students' academic performance at Loralai University was somewhat improved by both organization and critical thinking learning methodologies. The discussion included implications and suggestions for additional research.

Keywords: Organization, Critical Thinking, Learning Strategy, Students' Academic Performance

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Introduction

Balochistan's education system is changing and experiencing numerous obstacles. Municipal unrest, a lack of funding, and the country's economic crises caused the education sector to be greatly exaggerated, damaging learning services and necessitating the presence of qualified teachers, libraries, and laboratories to support the efficient conversion of knowledge and make the learning process available in Balochistan (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). To improve educational services and increase student learning results, it is necessary to address the concerns of excellence, access, governance, and management (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). As a result, the government of Balochistan has been addressing the country's educational issues for more than ten years through the Ministry of Education (MoE), partners, and donors. For instance, the Global Partnership for Education (GPE), formerly known as the Education for All Track project, provides more than 65 rising country partners to ensure that every child receives a high-quality basic education (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). Between 2004 and 2010, GPE contributed US\$2.2 billion in funding, enabling an estimated 19 million children to attend school. Regarding Pakistan, the World Bank places financial restrictions on the cooperation, which is being implemented by the governments of Balochistan and Sindh.

After the Baluchistan education sector plan 2013-2017 was approved, the Pakistani government joined the Global Partnership for Education in 2012. US\$34 million of the US\$100 million allotted for Pakistan was given to Balochistan (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). The Global Partnership for Education provides financial support to the government's Balochistan Secondary Education Section, which is in charge of implementing the country's educational program. UNICEF is the organizing agency, and the World Bank is the overseeing body behind the initiative in Pakistan. The projects cover the four primary subject areas of the 2013–18 Balochistan Education Sector Plan. i.e., access, equity, quality, and governance across the province's thirty-one communal sector education districts (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). One hundred twenty schools will be advanced to the next level (95 primary schools to middle and 25 middle schools to secondary/higher secondary level) over the three-year project, which will also establish 725 gender-neutral primary schools. The Balochistan government, which is responsible for educating its citizens, annually provides fiscal support to the Ministry of Education in order to plunder the education industry. This is in keeping with the government of Balochistan's lawful mandate to grant every Baloch equal access to facilities and educational opportunities in order to protect the country's social, economic, and political well-being (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). Because of this, the Balochistan Education Law mandates the state's basic education, which is defined as providing children in grades 1 through 9 with free, compulsory, and high-quality education in accordance with Article 25A.

Unfortunately, however, due to a number of obstacles, including limited access to learning resources, Article 25A is not being fully implemented (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). In accordance with global standards, the Ministry of Education in Balochistan works with relevant stakeholders and their adherents to achieve the goal of sustainable expansion, which aims to ensure equitable and comprehensive quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. The Ministry receives the best approaches and education sector plan. This reinforces the need for partners and administration to continue holding the industry accountable (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017). Some of the accomplishments that the government and donors of Balochistan have instigated include the provision of textbooks, educational materials, and teacher guides; the construction and renovation of schools; the provision of education services in accordance with national policies; and the effective implementation of faculty development programs for school administrators, teachers, and parent-teacher relationships. Notwithstanding the contributions made thus far, Balochistan pupils' educational performance remains unimpressive; passing rates for the ninth and twelfth grades on local examinations have significantly decreased (Gbollie & Keamu, 2017).

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the relation of Critical Thinking learning strategy and Organization Learning Strategy with Students' GPA in University classrooms.
2. To examine the relation of Critical Thinking learning strategy and Organization Learning Strategy with Gender in University classrooms.

Research Questions of the Study

1. What is the relation between Critical Thinking learning strategy and organizational learning Strategy in students' GPA in University classrooms?
2. What is the relation of Critical Thinking learning strategy and Organization Learning Strategy with Gender in University classrooms?

Hypothesis of the Study

1. The critical thinking and organization learning strategies will positively correlate with students' GPAs in university classrooms.
2. The Critical Thinking learning strategy and Organization Learning Strategies will positively correlate with Gender in University classrooms.

Scope/Significance of the Study

Be mindful that these perceptions—students' learning strategies and motivations—come at a price. Because it developed the motivational beliefs and learning strategies used by University of Loralai students to enroll in many disciplines, including Teacher Education in Pakistan, Assessment and Evaluation, Leadership and Management, Curriculum Development, etc., this research was quite lucrative. Additionally, it outlines possible obstacles to students' learning and offers suggestions for improvement. Academic standing at Loralai University. The research findings are thought to help students, producers, and politicians understand University of Loralai students' motivation and application of learning strategies in a clear and transparent manner. Encourage education and learning by pushing policies and initiatives that pique interest in nation-building.

Delimitations of the Study

A researcher conducted the study in a particular boundary of the University of Loralai to identify the learning strategies highly preferred by students of the University of Loralai. This study was conducted in the time duration of 6 months. A researcher utilizes resources such as a laptop, self-reported notes, the internet, articles, etc. A researcher collects data from higher-level students of the University of Loralai.

Literature Review

A study on the nature of motivational tactics and purported barriers to learning that Liberian junior and senior high school pupils face was carried out in 2016 in Liberia by Charles Gbollie and Harriett Pearl Keamu (Gbollie & Keamu, [2017](#)). The implementation of learning methodologies and motivation of students play a critical role in achieving civilized learning results. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the relationship between Liberian junior and senior high school students' educational presentation and their motivating beliefs and strategies (Gbollie & Keamu, [2017](#)). It also investigates the factors impeding their learning. Twelve learning barriers were predicted using a quantitative research methodology that collected cross-sectional data from 323 participants using motivated methods for learning questionnaires (Gbollie & Keamu, [2017](#)). The results of the analysis of the data using SPSS 17.0 reveal that the motivational belief is the most recommended belief, while test anxiety is the least preferred belief among all the learning strategies. Rehearsal strategies are acknowledged as the most popular learning strategies, while help-seeking is the least popular. This study established the existence of both positive relationships and also understood the relationship between learning strategy and motivating belief. A negative association occurs when both variables are inversely proportional to one another, i.e., when both variables grow concurrently or when they are directly proportional to one another (Gbollie & Keamu, [2017](#)).

Academic performance and learning strategies: a comparison between standard entrance undergraduates and accredited previous experiential learning (APEL) observed. In Malaysia, Fen Tan studied 400 undergraduates using a correlation research methodology. Data were gathered by questionnaires, and SPSS was used for independent t-test analysis (Tan, Eak, Oo, & Abdullah, [2021](#)). This study identifies the association between academic performance and the kinds of learning strategies employed by ordinary entry undergraduates and APEL, as well as the correlation between the two (Tan, Eak, Oo, & Abdullah, [2021](#)). According to the study, there aren't many differences between these two groups' learning processes. Regular students performed somewhat better than APEL students in both groups; however, the most preferred time and study environment management techniques are those that include regulating effort, while the least preferred strategies involve managing time (Tan, Eak, Oo, & Abdullah, [2021](#)). There is no connection between students' academic achievement and their cognitive abilities or peer learning. The academic performance of regular students is impacted by methods such as meta-cognitive self-regulation and aid-seeking, but not that of APEL undergraduates (Tan, Eak, Oo, & Abdullah, [2021](#)).

In order to examine self-regulated tactics, academic performance, and pleasure, Jenifer Lee Price performed research at Old Dominion University in 2017 (Price, [2017](#)). Data is gathered from 102 high school graduates who participated. Price ([2017](#)) employs a mixed method design to assess the data, which indicates a high or positive

correlation between self-regulated learning processes and satisfaction. Academic performance and SRL have no statistically meaningful relationship. According to Price (2017), effort regulation is highly preferred for academic success and is statistically not significant.

Excellent school chemistry students in O'hana, Hawaii, are the subject of a study to determine the association between self-regulatory learning practices and excellent academic achievements (Judd, 2005). Sixty-one male students are interviewed using a 14-item questionnaire to determine the most popular learning tactics before, during, and following the testing session (Judd, 2005). Additionally, it has been determined that high achievement levels support the use of self-regulatory learning techniques for exam preparation and that self-regulation enhances performance (Judd, 2005).

To elucidate the relationship between learning methods' mediating role and academic accomplishment in regard to achievement goals (Shehzad & Aziz, 2019). A study was conducted at Islamabad's Quaid-e-Azam University. Three hundred twenty-one students' responses to motivated techniques for learning and achievement goal questionnaires are utilized to gather data (Shehzad & Aziz, 2019). The findings state that learning techniques and academic accomplishments have a favorable impact on achievement objectives and that there is a substantial relationship between mastery approach and performance approach goals (Shehzad & Aziz, 2019). Additionally, it is disclosed that learning strategies related to resource management are thought to act as a mediator between goals and academic achievements, while learning strategies related to cognitive and metacognitive processes do not act as a mediator between mastery avoidance and performance approach and academic achievements (Shehzad & Aziz, 2019).

1. Students who are concerned with improving their skills are the mastery approach aims.
2. The purpose of mastery avoidance is to prevent students from making mistakes.
3. The performance method aims to make pupils appear intelligent and demonstrate their abilities to others.
4. Performance avoidance objectives: pupils learn to prevent appearing foolish or receiving subpar grades.

Spanish university students' perceptions of their emotional intelligence and their approaches to learning (Vega-Hernández et al., 2017). A study with a sample size of 2334 Spanish university students is carried out in a Spanish university to assess the relationship between students' perceived emotional intelligence and their learning process, particularly in the use of learning strategies (Vega-Hernández et al., 2017). Applying the TMMS-24 and abridges results in low values in the use of cognitive and control learning methods on the PEI dimensions, while high scores on learning support strategies are favorably correlated with high attention clarity and emotional recovery. However, high emotional attention is associated with female students' high scores on cognitive control and learning support 25 (Vega-Hernández et al., 2017).

Academic performance in medical students is correlated with learning-related emotions, metacognitive techniques, and academic self-efficacy (Almoslamani, 2022). Research has been gathered to explain the relationship between academic self-efficacy and performance, as well as the impact of metacognitive learning strategies and learning-related emotions on these relationships (Hayat et al., 2020). Data was gathered from 279 medical students at Shiraz University of Medical Sciences using three questionnaires. Data is analyzed using SPSS and clever PLS3 after academic emotion questionnaires (AEQ), metacognitive learning techniques, and academic self-efficacy questionnaires are completed (Hayat et al., 2020). The study's findings assess how students' self-efficacy influences their emotions connected to learning and their use of metacognitive learning strategies, both of which have an impact on the student's academic performance (Hayat et al., 2020). Additionally, understanding associated emotions influences Metacognitive learning techniques, which in turn moderate the effects of emotions on academic achievement. The study's findings showed that metacognitive learning techniques and learning-related emotions may have a mediation effect on the relationship between academic performance and self-efficacy, hence influencing students' academic performance (Hayat et al., 2020).

An investigation of the relationship between motivation and academic success is carried out in Singapore (Rotgans & Schmidt, 2012). Using the Motivated Techniques for Learning Questionnaire (MSLQ), 1,166 polytechnic students in Singapore provide data for the measurement of their motivational beliefs and self-regulated learning techniques

(Rotgans & Schmidt, 2012). In addition to analyzing the students' prior knowledge, academic achievements, and achievement-related classroom behaviors, it was determined that learning strategies and achievement-related classroom behaviors had an impact on the relationship between motivation and achievement rather than directly relating the two. Prior success is a strong indicator of future success, but it has no bearing on students' motivation (Rotgans & Schmidt, 2012).

The purpose of the study, which involved students at Saudi Arabia University, was to examine learning methodologies that are suitable for students' academic backgrounds and gender (Almoslamani, 2022). The model has 365 students, and the extent is on the ACRA-C scale. The two most popular techniques among almost everyone are microstrategies and revision habits (Almoslamani, 2022). It is randomly selected, and the disparity in learning approaches was observed in both male and female students, with a tendency in female students (Almoslamani, 2022). Additionally, the students highlight the significance of learning strategies as a predictor of their success in school (Almoslamani, 2022).

In order to evaluate learning processes, a survey of higher education students at Lima University was conducted (Alarcón et al., 2019). This study uses a qualitative approach, gathering data through interviews and direct examination techniques from beginning to end (Alarcón et al., 2019). The results of this revision demonstrate the application of three learning strategies: the metacognitive strategy, context control, and knowledge dissemination strategy (Alarcón et al., 2019).

In order to assess the intellectual concert and product outlook based on learning techniques, a study on medical responders was carried out at Shahid Behesht University of Tehran (Nabizadeh et al., 2019). Academic performance is used to determine the effectiveness of education; if student performance is strong and well-rounded, this indicates that a teacher is using an appropriate and effective teaching strategy (Nabizadeh, Hajian, Sheikhan, & Rafiei, 2019). Three hundred eighty respondents, both male and female, provided the data. To compile data on students' outcomes expectations and motivational learning practices, two scales are worn (Nabizadeh et al., 2019). The investigation's result, which tests educational accomplishment based on CGPA, indicates that there is little difference in CGPA, product expectations, and learning methodologies depending on gender, region, and marital status. Learning tactics and motivational strategies are directly related (Nabizadeh et al., 2019).

Research Methodology

Research Design

In this study, 300 participants used a quantitative research design. There were 119 females and 181 males in the population. They were selected from the University of Lorelai's Department of Education. The university was chosen after taking into account the various traits of the enrolled pupils. Only students in the following grades were included in the random selection process: BS, 1.5 (BE.d), 2.5 (BE.d), and M.Phil. Maximum of 1–50 students in each class on purpose; Ages 18–30 and above, taking into account their reading comprehension to carefully and impartially answer research questions and objectives; and remaining time before they finish their degree programs.

Population

All University of Lorelai and Education Department students made the population of this study. A sample was deprived of this population through the random sampling technique. The details of the sample are given below.

Sample (Participants)

In this study, 300 participants used a quantitative research design. There were 119 females and 181 males in the population. They were selected from the University of Lorelai's Department of Education. The university was chosen after taking into account the various traits of the enrolled pupils. Only students in the following grades were included in the random selection process: BS, 1.5 (BE.d), 2.5 (BE.d), and M.Phil. Maximum of 1–50 students in each class on purpose. Ages 18–30 years and above, taking into account their reading comprehension to carefully and impartially answer research questions and objectives, as well as the amount of time remaining before they finish their university degrees.

Research Instruments

My research instrument is a questionnaire through which I collected data. The names of the questionnaires are CTLS and OLS (Critical thinking learning strategy and organization learning strategy), which were designed by Pintrich and De Groot (1990). MSLQ has two parts, i.e, the Motivation strategies part and the learning strategies part. Again, the learning strategies part has five dimensions, which are Rehearsal, Elaboration, Organization, Critical Thinking, and Meta-cognitive self-regulation. Among these five dimensions, I am using CTLS and OLS for the research.

Since MSLQ seems to represent a useful, reliable, and valid questionnaire for assessing students' learning strategies, I did not construct my own questionnaire but rather adopted the MSLQ. MSLQ has a 4-point answer scale (4. Always use, 3. Often use, 2. Rarely use, 1. Never use). Scores of the scale were obtained by the average of the items within a scale.

Reliability of the Scale

The reliability of the scale was determined by the Cronbach Alpha coefficient using SPSS. Its value was 0.6, which shows good reliability of the scale, as shown by the following table.

Table 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.611	.669	5

Research Procedure

For the whole academic year, university students were permitted to take part in the study. It was anticipated at this point that they would have some motivating beliefs and be employing techniques meant to help them advance. There was a university-level consultation. I spoke with my supervisor to get the justification and objectives of the study, and the department head gave the study his or her approval and a letter of authorization while requesting the participation of university students. Students from the University of Loralai were permitted to take part in the research. By now, it was assumed that kids would have some motivating beliefs and be employing tactics to either succeed or fail in order to go on to the next grade level.

The questionnaire has well-written questions about learning strategies and motivating attitudes. The University of Loralai students who collected the data were taught data-collecting methodologies and fundamental research ethics to improve their performance. There was a pretest for the questionnaire. Within twenty to thirty minutes, the participants finished the questionnaire.

Data Presentation and Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistical Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the demographic variables in the form of frequency and percentage. The percentage and frequency of all demographic variables are shown in the form of tables and graphs.

Gender

The researcher analyzed the gender variable in the form of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 2

Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	181	60.3
Female	119	39.7
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart

Figure 1

Gender

Marital Status

The researcher analyzed the Marital Status variable in the form of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 3

Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Married	48	16.0
unmarried	252	84.0
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 2

Marital Status

Area

The researcher analyzed the area variable in terms of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 4

Area

Area	Frequency	Percent
Rural	127	42.3
Urban	173	57.7
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 2

Area

Age in years

The researcher analyzed the age in years variable in terms of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 4

Age in years

Age in years	Frequency	Percent
18-22	17	5.7
22-26	155	51.7
26-30	107	35.7
above30	21	7.0
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the Histogram chart.

Figure 3

Age in years

Number of Students in Class

The researcher analyzed the number of student variables in the form of frequency and percentage, which are shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 5

Number of students in class

No students in class	Frequency	Percent
1-5	6	2.0
1-10	27	9.0
1-20	156	52.0
1-30	96	32.0
1-40	12	4.0
1-50	3	1.0
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 4

Number of students in class

Program of study

The researcher analyzed the program of study variable in the form of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 6

Program of study

Program of study	Frequency	Percent
BS	139	46.3
Bed (1.5)	54	18.0
Bed (2.5)	107	35.7
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 5

Program of study

Educational Year

The researcher analyzed the educational year variable in terms of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 6

Educational year

Educational Year	Frequency	Percent
1st year	21	7.0
2nd year	155	51.7
3rd year	86	28.7
4th year	38	12.7
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 7

Program of study

University Name

The researcher analyzed the university variable in terms of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 7

University Name

University Name	Frequency	Percent
University of Loralai	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 6

University Name

Department Name

The researcher analyzed the department variable in terms of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 8

Department name

Department Name	Frequency	Percent
Education	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 7

Department name

GPA

The researcher analyzed the GPA variable in the form of frequency and percentage, which is shown in the form of a table and graph.

Table 9

GPA

GPA	Frequency	Percent
2-2.5	15	5.0
2.5-3.0	49	16.3
3.0-3.5	123	41.0
3.5-4	113	37.7
Total	300	100.0

The above table is also shown by the pie chart.

Figure 8

GPA

Inferential Data Analysis

Spearman's Correlation Analysis

Table 10

Correlations

			GPA	Mean_CTLS	Mean_OLS
Spearman's rho	GPA	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.104	.085
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.071	.143
		N	300	300	300
	Mean_ CTLS	Correlation Coefficient	.104	1.000	.515 ^{**}
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.071	.	.000
		N	300	300	300
	Mean_ OLS	Correlation Coefficient	.085	.515 ^{**}	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.143	.000	.
		N	300	300	300

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion of Results

The results of this study demonstrated that the academic performance of APEL and normal undergraduates differs significantly. It is consistent with the results presented by Latifah et al. (2009) and Awang et al. (2014). Cheng and Siow (2018), however, found no discernible performance difference between these two student groups. The discrepancy between the results of the previous research and the present study may be attributed to institutional factors, including the university's support, the program's quality, the skill of the teaching staff, and the rapport between students and instructors/tutors among other things. To date, every study, including this one, has only looked at students from a single ODL university. It's possible that some schools have superior support systems that let APEL entry kids function on par with standard entry pupils. Future research can compare these two student groups' academic performance across many ODL universities. There was no discernible difference between these two student groups when a t-test was performed to compare the learning strategies employed by these two undergraduate groups. Academic performance was favorably connected with time and study environment management, effort regulation, and both for normal and APEL entrance students. Scheduling, planning, allocating study time, and controlling the whole study environment are all included in time and study environment management. Academic task management is known as effort regulation. It shows how dedicated the students remained in the face of challenges or setbacks (Pintrich et al., 1991). Students in this study with higher CGPA ratings also scored highly on these two sub-scales. Similar findings were observed by Neroni et al. (2019), Radovan (2011), Puzziferro (2008), and Agricola et al. (2012), who evaluated nontraditional learners (students 24 years of age and above). Adult ODL learners encountered numerous obstacles in their education, including attending classes off-campus and juggling employment and family responsibilities (Ronning, 2009). As such, it is imperative that they develop a high degree of self-control. According to Patrick (2004), students who are able to control and manage their study environment are better able to focus, avoid distractions, and ultimately achieve academic success.

Peer learning and academic performance did not significantly correlate for either ordinary or APEL newcomers. The mean score for peer learning in this study was the lowest when compared to the mean score for all learning strategies, which is consistent with the findings published by Puzziferro (2008). Similar to Puzziferro (2008), it is advised that further research be done in order to gain a deeper understanding of the lack of peer learning among ODL learners, irrespective of whether they are regular or APEL entrants. This is because a number of factors that were not examined in this study may have an impact on this phenomenon. According to Duncan and McKeachie (2005),

metacognitive self-regulation entails organizing, tracking, and managing one's own learning. Certain researchers (Neroni et al., 2012; Agricola et al., 2012)

It has also been noted that for remote learners, metacognitive self-regulation is a favorable predictor of academic success. Neroni et al. (2019) went on to say that while ODL learners are preoccupied with their families and jobs, metacognitive self-regulation is crucial. Only the ordinary entrants' metacognitive self-regulation scores in this study were positively connected with their academic achievement; the APEL entrants' metacognitive self-regulation scores did not correspond significantly with their academic performance. Why meta-cognitive self-regulation is uncorrelated with APEL applicants' academic achievement requires more research.

Similarly, asking for assistance has a favorable correlation with the academic achievement of ordinary entrants but not with APEL entrants. The literature contains inconsistent results. Help-seeking behavior is negatively correlated with academic performance, according to Neroni et al. (2019); however, Cred_e and Phillips (2011) found no correlation between these two factors. Regular participants in the study who had previously completed conventional studies did not hesitate to ask for assistance from others when they encountered problems since they had been trained to do so whenever they needed clarification or aid in understanding a concept. In contrast, APEL applicants might not be accustomed to asking for assistance from others because of past experiences that made them believe that doing so is a sign of weakness and that they should instead take care of themselves.

The conclusion that there is no meaningful correlation between academic achievement and cognitive strategies—which included organization, elaboration, rehearsal, and critical thinking—was startling. These results go counter to those of Neroni et al. (2019), who found that a few cognitive skills were positively correlated with academic achievement. They found that academic achievement was not correlated with simple cognitive abilities or academic thinking but that academic performance was positively predicted by complex cognitive skills. One possible explanation for the inconsistent results could be the variation in the subjects chosen. While all undergraduate students at a university, whether they were in their first year, midway through their studies, or their final year, participated in the current study, the participants in the Neroni et al. (2019) study were students who were 14 months after they had first enrolled in the university. Some students may not yet have acquired the cognitive techniques when they are still adjusting to their university studies. Students who were able to use the cognitive methods thus fared better than their colleagues who had not yet learned them. All undergraduate students, varying in their academic phases, were included in the current study as participants. As they advance in their studies, some pupils may have picked up these learning practices. This could be the cause of the lack of a discernible relationship between academic achievement and cognitive abilities. Therefore, more investigation is required to examine the connection between students' academic achievement at various stages of their studies and their learning styles.

Conclusion

It means that 100% of students were Muslims. Gender-wise, the frequency of male students was 181, and female students were 119. Regarding marital status, the frequency of married students was 48, and that of unmarried students was 252. The area-wise, the frequency of the urban area was 173, while the frequency of the rural area was 127. Regarding age in years, the frequency of 18-22 years students was 17, 22-26 years was 155, 26-30 years students was 107, and above 30 years students was 21. Regarding the program of study, the frequency of (BS) students was 139, while the frequency of (BE.d) 1.5 students was 54, and the frequency of (BE.d 2.5) students was 107. Regarding educational year, the frequency of 1st-year students was 21, 2nd-year students were 155, 3rd-year students were 86, and 4th-year students were 38. Regarding GPA, the frequency of 2-2.5GPA students was 15, 2.5-3.0GPA students was 49, 3.0-3.5GPA students was 123, and 3.5-4.0GPA students was 113.

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